

A Case Study on Out Bounding Corporate Social Responsibility of Selected Indian Banks to Enhance Customer

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: India's banking sector contributes to the nation's overall economy by helping to mobilize deposits and lending money to people, businesses, and other sectors of the economy. A new government regulation mandates that banks, both public and private, voluntarily donate two percent of their revenues to corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives that address a range of societal challenges. It's interesting to read about how Indian banks have applied CSR funding. It will be interesting to compare the CSR programs of a few Indian public and private banks to observe how nimbly they have increased organizational business benefits through outbound CSR expenditures.

Design/Methodology: This essay outlines, discusses, and assesses a number of outbound social responsibility initiatives that Indian banks have started or intend to start. A range of publicly available sources, such as the websites of the chosen institutions, relevant case studies, and bank publications, were used to compile the data.

Findings: Outbound CSR programs impact banks' capacity to attract new customers and retain current ones in a number of ways. Banks may build emotional ties with their clients, improve customer trust, and enhance their brand image. Based on an analysis of CSR initiatives by both public and private sector banks, it was discovered that whereas public banks provided indirect support for brand-building initiatives, private sector banks prioritized providing direct support for their client services. Because of this, both types of banks will benefit from increased customer satisfaction as well as, independently, from the marketing of their services to underrepresented populations through the use of a strategy that allocates a certain percentage of CSR money to outbound CSR initiatives.

Originality/Value: The purpose of this study is to determine if public and private banks have a role in the effective use of their CSR money for external CSR initiatives.

Keywords: Public and Private Banks, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Inbound CSR strategy, ABCD analysis, Customer attraction.

1. INTRODUCTION

A corporation is a necessary component of society. The different stakeholders in the community are essential to its growth and prosperity. Success or failure is entirely determined by society. The society provides these corporate entities with all the necessary inputs. The society also makes use of their goods and services. This gives corporate entities a lot of room to think and act in ways that will benefit and sustain society and its stakeholders. These corporate entities' responsibilities are known as "Corporate Social Responsibility." [1].

The various national and international level rules and notifications that are periodically released by various authorities have had a continual influence on corporate social responsibility in India. [2]. Nonetheless, the guidelines were of a voluntary nature. Corporate houses were not required to engage in CSR. [3]. Therefore, anything that they were doing was a voluntary action taken by the business houses. However, India's CSR policies have seen a significant shift as a result of the Companies Act, 2013. The aforementioned Act's provisions required CSR initiatives for a number of Indian company types. Researchers have compared the corporate social responsibility (CSR) policies of a few corporate public sector commercial banks with those of private sector commercial banks through the current study [4].

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Table 1: Review of literature on CSR activities of the Indian banks

S. No.		Focus	Reference
1	CSR in Canara bank	Supporting public health care, assisting with primary healthcare for students attending government schools Distributing free books to support education supporting primary education, providing jobs for the poor, developing young people's skills, and creating sustainable livelihoods.	Nandini Prabhu, G. (2021).[5].
2	CSR in union bank	Given their critical role in providing funding for global economic and developmental endeavors, financial institutions—including banks—have a significant impact on sustainable development. It is imperative in this regard that banks behave as conscientious corporate citizens in society, particularly in a developing nation like India.	Chaudhury, et al.(2012) [6].
3	CSR in state bank of India	Getting rid of hunger, poverty, and malnutrition, gender equity supporting preventative health care and cleanliness, supporting the Dominant Government's Swach Bharat Kosh initiative to promote sanitation and make safe drinking water available and promoting education, including special education and service-enhancing talent assistances, primarily between young people and the elderly.	Pomering, A., & Dolnicar, S. (2009).[7].
4	CSR in Bank of Baroda	The bank has always taken macro and micro initiatives that express its corporate social responsibility (CSR) vision for Maharashtra. It has constantly adopted the idea of returning a portion of what it has earned to society.	Moharana, S. (2013). [8]
5	CSR in ICICI bank	The ICICI Framework for Social Development (ICICI Foundation) or another organisation is responsible for the majority of the activities. Sustainability in the Environment Transformation of Society Water safety and Subsistence.	Kanji, G. K., & Chopra, P. K. (2010). [9]
6	CSR in HDFC bank	HDFC Bank's CSR Enhance our governance process by placing a focus on morality, transparency, and accountability. Effectively involving stakeholders will result in value creation for customers. Promote diversity, gender equity, and worker well-being. respect and uphold universally acknowledged human rights.	Burianová, L., & Paulík, J. [10]
7	CSR in Punjab national bank	The Bank regularly participates in CSR activities through RSETIs and FLCC centres as well as other CSR initiatives like contributions. contributes to socioeconomic advancement through a variety of initiatives in the following areas, increasing capabilities by teaching newer generations new skills.	Dogra, A., & Dogra, M. (2019).[11].
8	CSR in National bank	Medical care, sanitization, water consumption amenities, Education/Literacy, Women's rights approval Social Progress and Economic Development Advancement of monetary payments and other things.	Márquez, A., & Fombrun, C. J. (2005). [12]
9	CSR in Axis bank	It has proven to be quite innovative in terms of corporate social responsibility. For instance, Village Knowledge Centres and Famers' Clubs target the rural market. Additionally, they provide programmes for girls that pay for their education. other programmes.	Tai, F. M., & Chuang, S. H. (2014). [13]

10	CSR in Central Bank	Establishing livelihood initiatives, creche facilities for children from low-income families, children with special needs, workers' families, women and persons with disabilities.	Mita, A.F. et al. (2018). [14]
11	CSR in Corporation bank	The initiatives projects would be implemented in India, ideally in regions where the Bank has a presence. Programmes and projects that generate communal value by fusing commercial replications with social and environmental significances and practises will be given preference. Projects and programmes shouldn't be limited to the benefit of employees, their families, or those with disabilities.	Smith, N. C. (2003). [15]
12	CSR in Kotak Mahindra bank	The bank has always taken macro and micro initiatives that express its corporate social responsibility (CSR) vision for Maharashtra. It has constantly adopted the idea of returning a portion of what it has earned to society.	Bordolo, N., & Mukherje, D. K. (2017),[16].

3. RESEARCH GAP

To find out direct benefits to the banks to improve the brand image and goodwill.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- (1) To knowing important facets of banks' outbound corporate responsibilities:
- (2) To analysing new business by implementing outbound Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs to benefits the society.
- (3) To evaluating various outbound corporate responsibilities of private and public sectors banks to build brand image.
- (4) To analysing ABCD frame work of Private and public sectors bank

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The information is collected for this Case study & analysis, from bank websites as well as academic research publications that have been published in a variety of journals and conference proceedings. Using existing data, such as annual reports of public commercial banks and private commercial banks, CSR activity information is compared between private and public banks.

6. TO KNOWING IMPORTANT FACETS OF BANKS' OUTBOUND CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITIES

Banks' outbound corporate responsibilities are the duties and responsibilities they have outside of their own internal business affairs and activities. These obligations cover the environment, the global economy, and the larger community. The following are important facets of banks' outward corporate responsibilities [17].

6.1 Social responsibility:

- **Community development:** Banks are supposed to support the growth of the areas in which they conduct business. This could entail lending a hand to neighbourhood projects, charitable causes, and community development endeavors.
- **Financial Inclusion:** In order to promote financial inclusion and lessen economic inequities, banks should work to offer financial services to underserved and marginalized communities [18].

6.2 Environment:

- **Sustainable Practices:** It is recommended that banks implement ecologically sustainable practices in their day-to-day operations. This includes cutting back on waste, lessening their carbon impact, and encouraging environmentally beneficial projects.
- **Green Financing:** Banks can contribute to the funding of environmental sustainability-promoting projects including green infrastructure and renewable energy programs.

6.3 Moral Conduct in Banking:

- **Fair Lending Practices:** Banks must follow moral and just lending standards, guaranteeing that loans and other financial products are provided to all customers equally and in accordance with applicable laws.
- **Transparency:** Banks should operate in a transparent manner, providing pertinent information to all relevant parties, such as investors, consumers, and regulatory bodies [19].

6.4 Management of Companies:

- **Accountability:** Banks ought to uphold strict corporate governance guidelines, including transparent accountability frameworks and commitment to moral business conduct.
- **Risk management:** Making sure that risk management procedures are appropriate in order to protect the interests of investors and customers, among other stakeholders.

6.5 Financial Stability:

Banks are essential to preserving the stability of the financial system because they uphold systemic stability. They are supposed to contribute to the general stability of the economy and exercise responsible risk management.

6.6 Regulatory Responsibilities and Compliance:

- **Legal Compliance:** Local, national, and international laws and regulations pertaining to the financial sector must be complied with by banks. This covers know your customer (KYC) and anti-money laundering (AML) laws [20].
- **Data Privacy and Security:** Banks are in charge of protecting consumer information and making sure that financial transactions are secure.

6.7 Global Responsibility:

- **Anti-Corruption Measures:** Banks should put in place measures to eliminate bribery and corruption in their internal operations as well as in their interactions with partners and clients.
- **International Standards:** In order to foster uniformity and dependability in the international financial system, banks are urged to abide by best practices and international standards [21]

6.8 Workplace Diversity and Inclusion:

Banks should support a diverse and inclusive workplace that upholds equitable treatment and equal opportunities for all workers.

- **Training and Development:** Offering continuous training and development opportunities to staff members so they may improve their abilities and make valuable contributions to the company.

6.9 Customer Protection:

- **Fair methods:** Banks should make sure that their services and products are transparent and that they use fair and responsible lending and banking methods to safeguard the interests of their clients [22].

6.10 Innovation and Technology Responsibilities:

- **Digital Ethics:** As technology plays a bigger role in banking, organizations need to respect moral principles when using digital tools and data to safeguard transaction security and preserve consumer privacy.

Figure 1: Outbound responsibilities of Banks

Author's Source

7. NEW BUSINESS BY IMPLEMENTING OUTBOUND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY (CSR) PROGRAMS THAT BENEFITS THE SOCIETY

Like any other company, Indian banks can draw in new business by implementing outbound Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs that also benefit society. The following are some tactics Indian banks may want to think about:

1. **Financial Literacy Programs:** Educate people and businesses on proper money management through the implementation of financial literacy programs. Providing financial literacy can improve the bank's reputation and draw in customers who are looking for financial advice [23].
2. **Inclusive banking and microfinance:** Put an emphasis on offering financial services to communities that are underprivileged and face economic hardship. To demonstrate the bank's dedication to inclusive banking practices, microfinance efforts can be emphasized.
3. **Assistance with Agriculture and Rural Development:** Allocate funds towards initiatives that bolster farmers and rural development. This can be funding agricultural projects, giving farmers low-interest loans, or helping to maintain rural infrastructure. This not only benefits the community at large but also reaches a sizable consumer base in rural locations.
4. **Health Initiatives:** Work with health groups to promote health-related projects, plan health camps, or offer medical services. This can solve important social concerns and improve the bank's reputation.
5. **Education and Skill Development:** Fund educational initiatives, scholarship programs, and programs for skill development. This is in line with the national aim to improve education and employability in addition to benefiting the community.
6. **Environmental Sustainability Initiatives:**
 - Fund environmentally conscious initiatives and encourage sustainable lifestyles. Customers who care about the environment may find this appealing, and the bank's standing as a socially conscious organization may benefit [24].
7. **Community Empowerment and Engagement:**
 - Take part in community development initiatives, such as constructing infrastructure, assisting nearby companies, or generating job possibilities. Proving your dedication to community welfare can draw clients who appreciate these kinds of programs.
8. **Disaster Relief and Rehabilitation:** Create a strong corporate social responsibility program for both relief and rehabilitation. Engaging in proactive relief efforts following natural disasters can yield favorable media coverage and draw in clients who value the bank's social responsibility [25].
9. **Financial Inclusion and Digital Literacy:**
 - Implement initiatives to advance financial inclusion and digital literacy, particularly in rural regions. This places the bank in a position to support financial empowerment projects and is in line with government initiatives.

10. **Collaborations with NGOs and Social entrepreneurs:** To carry out CSR projects, work with respectable NGOs and social entrepreneurs. By collaborating with well-known institutions, the bank broadens the scope of its social influence and lends legitimacy to its initiatives.
11. **Transparency and Reporting:** Make sure that CSR efforts are communicated in a transparent manner. Reports on the effects of CSR activities should be released on a regular basis to demonstrate measurable results and reaffirm the bank's dedication to social responsibility [26].

By incorporating these tactics into their CSR programs, Indian banks stand out in a crowded market and draw in clients who respect socially conscious banking in addition to making a significant contribution to the advancement of society.

Banks prioritize consumer security because financial transactions are delicate and customers have confidence in financial organizations. To ensure the security of their customers, financial institutions employ a variety of tactics in both traditional banking and the increasingly digitalized world. Important components of a bank's duty to safeguard the security of its customers include the following:

1. **Data protection:** Banks are in charge of protecting client data, which includes financial and personal information. To avoid identity theft, data breaches, and unauthorized access, this entails putting strong data protection mechanisms in place [27].
2. **Cyber security:** To defend their networks and systems from online attacks, banks make significant investments in cyber security measures. To protect client data and transactions, this entails putting intrusion detection systems, firewalls, and encryption technologies in place.
3. **Authentication and Authorization:** To guarantee that only those with permission can access customer accounts, banks use multi-factor authentication techniques. Usually, a mix of security tokens, PINs, passwords, and biometric authentication is used for this.
4. **Fraud Prevention:** To detect and stop fraudulent activity, banks use advanced fraud detection systems. This entails keeping an eye on transactions for odd trends, spotting unauthorized access, and applying artificial intelligence to data analysis to find possible fraud indications [28].
5. **Secure Transactions:** Banks place a high focus on guaranteeing the security of transactions made via mobile and internet platforms. To preserve the integrity and confidentiality of transactions, secure coding techniques, encrypted sensitive data during transmission, and secure connections (like HTTPS) are used.

8. OUTBOUND CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITIES OF PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTORS BANKS TO BUILD BRAND IMAGE

In addition to its main banking operations, Canara Bank, like many other financial firms, is expected to participate in outbound corporate social responsibilities (CSR). An outbound CSR bank like Canara Bank might concentrate its efforts in the following basic areas,

1. **Financial Inclusion:** Canara Bank may take part in programs that support financial inclusion by extending its reach to underprivileged and economically disadvantaged populations and offering them banking services [29].
2. **Education and Skill Development:** In order to contribute to the empowerment and upliftment of communities, support educational initiatives, scholarships, and skill development programs.
3. **Healthcare Initiatives:** To enhance the health and well-being of communities, funds are allocated to healthcare initiatives, medical facilities, and awareness campaigns.
4. **Environmental Sustainability:** Integrating eco-friendly procedures into the bank's operations and endorsing programs that promote preservation and sustainability of the environment [30].
5. **Community Development:** To enhance the standard of living for the communities where it conducts business, Canara Bank may take part in community development projects like infrastructure construction, sanitation campaigns, and other activities.
6. **Rural Development:** concentrating on initiatives that address the particular difficulties that rural communities have, such as bolstering agriculture, developing rural infrastructure, and enhancing livelihoods.
7. **Women Empowerment:** Canara Bank may launch programs to help women entrepreneurs, encourage gender equality, and provide financial literacy in order to empower women both socially and economically [31].
8. **CSR Funding:** As required by law, cash must be set aside for particular CSR initiatives and programs that address social and environmental problems.
9. **Staff involvement in societal :** Encourage and assist staff members in engaging in voluntary work and community service, making use of their knowledge and abilities to advance societal welfare.
10. **Financial Literacy Programs:** Planning and implementing financial literacy initiatives to raise people's financial literacy and awareness while also encouraging responsible financial behaviour [32].

11. **Assistance for Individuals with Disabilities:** Canara Bank may take part in programs that assist individuals with disabilities, such as offering accessibility in its branches and funding activities that increase societal inclusion.
12. **Disaster Relief and Rehabilitation:** Assisting with relief operations following natural disasters and taking part in initiatives aimed at assisting impacted communities in their recovery.
13. **Cultural and Art Initiatives:** Endorsing artistic and cultural projects that support community liveliness, foster artistic expression, and support the preservation of local heritage.
14. **Ethical Banking Practices:** Respecting moral principles and openness in business dealings, guaranteeing responsible and equitable lending, and adhering to all applicable laws and guidelines [33].

Table 2: Last 5 years CSR Spending of Canara Bank of India

S. No.	Year	Total Annual Profit (crores)	CSR Spending (crores)
1	2018	7,456	74.12
2	2019	8,895	67.98
3	2020	6,404.70	84.56
4	2021	11,654	95.45
5	2022	8,535	89.67

Author's Source**State Bank of India**

The outbound corporate social activities not only contribute to the welfare of society but also help banks build a positive reputation, enhance brand image, and foster long-term relationships with stakeholders. Additionally, they align with regulatory requirements and demonstrate a commitment to sustainable and responsible business practices. An outbound CSR bank like State Bank of India might concentrate its efforts in the following basic areas [34].

1. **Financial Inclusion:** Providing basic financial services to a larger population in order to facilitate and promote financial inclusion.
2. **Economic Development:** Various fiscal and monetary policies that support growth and stabilize the economy can help to promote economic development.
3. **Financial Stability:** Preserving financial stability through the application of laws and policies that guarantee the robustness and well-being of the financial system.
4. **Consumer Protection:** Putting in place safeguards, such as regulating and overseeing financial institutions, to safeguard consumers' interests in financial transactions.
5. **Financial Literacy:** Encouraging people to become financially literate and educated so they can make wise financial decisions.
6. **Regulatory Compliance:** To preserve the integrity of the financial system, it is imperative that financial institutions adhere to ethical norms and rules.
7. **Money supply and Management:** To maintain the stability of the monetary system, managing the supply and circulation of money is necessary.
8. **Payment Systems:** Coordinating and refining payment methods to provide safe and effective transactions [35].
9. **Supporting Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs):** • Implementing policies or programs that encourage the growth and development of SMEs, which are vital for economic development and employment.
10. **Environmental and Social Sustainability:** • Encouraging sustainable practices and integrating social and environmental factors into decision-making processes.
11. **Ethical Banking Practices:** Promoting moral conduct and conscientious banking methods among financial establishments.
12. **Cooperation with Other Stakeholders:** To address more general social concerns, governments, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and other stakeholders should collaborate [36].

Table 3: Last 5 years CSR Spending of State Bank of India

S. No.	Year	Total Annual Profit (crores)	CSR Spending (crores)
1	2018	9,765	99.78

2	2019	8,546	88.23
3	2020	7,345	76.90
4	2021	8,564	97.45
5	2022	11,897	84.83

Author's Source

ICICI Bank's dedication to sustainable development and community welfare is inextricably linked to its CSR initiatives. Remember that particular projects and specifics could change over time, so for the most up-to-date information, it's best to consult the most recent reports and updates from ICICI Bank. The following areas are where ICICI Bank has historically concentrated its CSR efforts:

- 1. Healthcare Initiatives:** Focusing on preventative healthcare, these initiatives support medical facilities, healthcare projects, and awareness campaigns to enhance community health and well-being [37].
- 2. Education & Skill Development:** To empower people and support the development of human capital, ICICI Bank invests in educational initiatives such as scholarships, the construction of school facilities, and skill-building programs.
- 3. Rural Development:** Implementing initiatives aimed at boosting sustainable farming methods, improving general rural infrastructure, and improving livelihoods.
- 4. Financial Inclusion:** By reaching out to underbanked and unbanked communities and giving them access to banking services and financial literacy initiatives, ICICI Bank helps promote financial inclusion.
- 5. Women Empowerment:** Endorsing programs that provide women with financial literacy, business opportunities, and social and economic empowerment; these include activities that advance gender equality [38].

Table 4: Last 5 years CSR Spending of ICICI Bank of India

S. No.	Year	Total Annual Profit (crores)	CSR Spending (crores)
1	2018	12,786	120.23
2	2019	11,348	99.87
3	2020	13,945	112.56
4	2021	12,978	95.78
5	2022	11,675	89.67

Author's Source

HDFC Bank

Outbound CSR activities enable HDFC Bank to fulfill its corporate citizenship responsibilities while simultaneously deriving strategic benefits for the organization.

- 1. Community Development:** Supporting community development by working on initiatives that deal with certain issues, like sanitization, infrastructure development, and community welfare.
- 2. Disaster Relief and Rehabilitation:** Supporting relief operations in the event of a disaster and taking part in community-benefiting rehabilitation initiatives.
- 3. Encourage staff members to actively engage :** in volunteer work and community service, using their knowledge and abilities to advance societal welfare.
- 4. Technology for Social Good:** Using technology to improve society, such as through programs that employ digital technologies to solve social issues and encourage inclusive growth. [39].
- 5. Skill Development and Livelihood Enhancement:** Implementing skill development programs, with an emphasis on underprivileged groups, can improve youth employability and encourage entrepreneurship.
- 6. Technology for Social Good:** Using technology to improve society, such as through programs that employ digital technologies to solve social issues and encourage inclusive growth.

Table 5: Last 5 years CSR Spending of HDFC Bank of India

S. No.	Year	Total Annual Profit (crores)	CSR Spending (crores)
1	2018	8,675	78.67
2	2019	7,456	99.72
3	2020	6,567	86.38
4	2021	8,567	90.64
5	2022	9,456	87.19

Author's Source**Kotak Mahindra Bank:**

Kotak Mahindra Bank's outbound CSR activities enable the organization to fulfill its corporate social responsibility while also deriving strategic benefits that contribute to its growth and sustainability.

- Skill Development and Livelihood Enhancement:** Implementing skill development programs, with an emphasis on underprivileged groups, can improve youth employability and encourage entrepreneurship.
- Environmental Sustainability:** Kotak Mahindra Bank may launch programs to assist eco-friendly projects, energy conservation, and green banking techniques, among other measures [40].

Table 6 : Last 5 years CSR Spending of **Kotak Mahindra** Bank of India

S. No.	Year	Total Annual Profit (crores)	CSR Spending (crores)
1	2018	8,421`	76.47
2	2019	7,056	64.34
3	2020	6,453	55.32
4	2021	7,538	76.98
5	2022	8,564	77.56

Author's Source**ABCD Analysis of CSR activities of the Banks :**

Banks like HDFC Bank and Kotak Mahindra Bank can obtain important insights into the opportunities, threats, weaknesses, and strengths related to their corporate social responsibility initiatives by performing an ABCD analysis of their CSR operations. Through improved performance review, resource allocation, and strategic decision-making, the banks are ultimately better able to generate shared value for the benefit of society and business.

Advantages

- Improved Reputation:** Banks can cultivate a favorable public perception by participating in outbound corporate responsibility programs. Customers, investors, and the community may become more trusting as a result, which would improve the bank's reputation [41].
- Stakeholder Trust and Loyalty:** Banks may cultivate trust and loyalty among their stakeholders by showcasing their dedication to social and environmental challenges. Support for a bank that actively promotes social well-being and is in line with the values of its clients, staff members, and investors may be higher.
- Risk Mitigation:** Banks can reduce a number of risks, such as reputational hazards, by implementing outbound corporate responsibility. Banks lessen the possibility of bad press, regulatory attention, and legal problems related to non-compliance by addressing social and environmental concerns [42].
- Competitive Advantage:** Banks can obtain a market advantage by incorporating ethical business practices. Customers are growing more aware of how their decisions affect the environment and society, therefore businesses that practice corporate responsibility can draw in and keep clients.
- Long-Term Sustainability:** Sustainable company practices and outbound corporate responsibility are frequently linked. In addition to improving societal well-being, banks that prioritize long-term sustainability set themselves up for success in an industry that is changing quickly.

Benefits:

1. **Engagement and Satisfaction of Employees:** Taking part in CSR initiatives can raise staff morale and satisfaction. Nowadays, a lot of workers appreciate their jobs at organizations that actively work to better society. In addition to attracting top personnel, CSR initiatives can enhance the culture of the workplace.
2. **Community Development:** As important financial institutions, banks are essential to the local economy. Banks can help infrastructure, healthcare, education, and other community development projects by investing through outbound corporate responsibility, which can have a positive knock-on effect on the economy [43].
3. **Beneficial Effect on the Environment:** Banks may solve environmental issues by utilizing their power and resources. The world is moving toward sustainability, and initiatives like green investing, sustainable financing, and lowering the environmental impact of operations help to make the earth healthier.
4. **Adherence to Regulations:** Numerous areas and authorities are enforcing rules that promote or mandate corporate social responsibility. Proactively adopting CSR efforts by banks guarantees adherence to changing legal and regulatory environments.
5. **Customer and Market Insights:** Banks may learn a lot about consumer preferences and market trends by participating in CSR initiatives. Product development, marketing campaigns, and strategic decision-making can all benefit from this knowledge.

While there are many advantages to outbound corporate responsibility efforts, banks may also encounter certain drawbacks and difficulties.

Challenges:

1. **Financial Costs:** Funding is frequently needed to implement outbound corporate responsibility programs. Increased costs for community development initiatives, sustainability initiatives, and charitable giving may be borne by banks, thereby affecting their short-term profitability.
2. **Resource Diversion:** Concentrating on corporate responsibility programs may take time, energy, and resources away from the bank's primary business operations. The competitiveness and operating efficiency of this diversion may be impacted.
3. **Green washing Risks:** Banks that participate in flimsy or deceptive corporate responsibility initiatives to project a favorable image without making meaningful contributions run the danger of engaging in greenwashing. Reputational harm may result if stakeholders believe these efforts are insufficient or not honest [44].
4. **Mismatched Stakeholder Expectations:** Expectations from various stakeholders about corporate responsibility may differ. It can be difficult to strike a balance between the many interests of clients, investors, staff, and communities, and not living up to these expectations can leave people unhappy.
5. **Complexity in Measurement and Reporting:** It can be difficult to precisely calculate the return on investment and quantify the impact of corporate responsibility programs. Establishing clear reporting guidelines and defining key performance indicators (KPIs) for their contributions to the environment and society may be difficult tasks for banks [45].

Disadvantages:

1. **Difficulties with Regulatory Compliance:** The corporate responsibility regulatory environment is always changing, and banks may encounter difficulties in understanding and adhering to a wide range of rules. There may be legal and reputational repercussions from noncompliance.
2. **Potential for Mission Drift:** If banks get too entangled in a wide range of corporate responsibility programs, they run the risk of losing sight of their main financial goals. Deviating from the primary objective of providing financial services may have an effect on the bank's overall success.
3. **Opposition from Shareholders:** A portion of shareholders might put financial gains ahead of corporate social duty. Banks may face conflict with shareholders who place a higher priority on maximizing earnings and dividends if they devote a large number of resources to CSR initiatives. [46].
4. **Globalization Challenges:** Banks with international operations may find it difficult to match CSR programs with various social, cultural, and environmental settings. It might be difficult to adjust to various international norms and expectations.
5. **Competitive Disadvantage:** While corporate responsibility can give banks a competitive edge, there's a chance that they could lose out if rivals don't take similar steps. This is particularly true if investors and customers value conventional financial success more highly than CSR initiatives.

To summarise, banks must exercise caution while navigating potential difficulties like as financial expenses, stakeholder expectations, regulatory challenges, and greenwashing threats, even though outbound corporate responsibility can have beneficial consequences. This is to ensure that their CSR activities are sustainable and effective.

9. FINDINGS

- (1) The study suggests that certain banks, such as ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, and State Bank of India, which rank among the best in terms of development and effectiveness, may not be investing as much in CSR as they need be in order to meet their organizational objectives.
- (2) We were unable to find any inbound activities offered by the aforementioned six banks using the partial funding of CSR, based on our case studies of these institutions. In order to effectively employ CSR money for the development and provision of green banking services and to lessen the additional financial burden, it is recognized that the banking sector lacks smart strategy and, consequently, clever leaders.

10. SUGGESTIONS

- (1) An analysis of the leading banks in both the public and private sectors reveals that even while both are contributing to CSR practices, this is still insufficient. To please clients, banks should take part in more incoming CSR activities. They can achieve this by employing the astute tactic of using CSR funds for inward initiatives like creating and providing green banking services under the guise of environmental sustainability.
- (2) The bank ought to appoint knowledgeable, skilled professionals who are conversant with the fundamentals of sustainable banking. These individuals can ensure that CSR funds are distributed correctly and provide insightful advice.

11. CONCLUSION

Banks may differentiate themselves in the market, improve employee morale, develop emotional connections with customers, improve their brand image, and foster positive word-of-mouth by showcasing their commitment to social responsibility. It is the corporate duty of banks to attract customers. "Corporate social responsibility" (CSR) describes how banks engage with their customers and communities. Enhancing the organization and environment is the aim of these programs. It was found that banks' ability to foster social peace can be significantly impacted by well-executed CSR initiatives.

References

- [1] Patjoshi, P. K., & Nayak, U. (2020). Impact of CSR on Financial Performance: A Study on Banking Companies in India. *International Journal of Modern Agriculture*, 9(3), 953-962.
- [2] Hu, V. I., & Scholtens, B. (2014). Corporate social responsibility policies of commercial banks in developing countries. *Sustainable Development*, 22(4), 276-288.
- [3] Singh, N., Srivastava, R., & Rastogi, R. (2015). Lighting the lamp of education: Role of Indian banking sector towards the corporate social responsibility in achieving development goals. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 3(1), 440-446.
- [4] Jamali, D. (2007). The case for strategic corporate social responsibility in developing countries. *Business and Society Review*, 112(1), 1-27
- [5] Nandini Prabhu, G. (2021). Green Banking Practices – A Case Study on Indian Green Banking System. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*. 2(3), 487-493.
- [6] Chaudhury, S. K., Das, S. K., & Sahoo, P. K. (2012). Practices of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in banking sector in India: An assessment. *Research Journal of Economics, Business and ICT*, 4(1), 76-81.
- [7] Pomeroy, A., & Dolnicar, S. (2009). Assessing the prerequisite of successful CSR implementation: are consumers aware of CSR initiatives? *Journal of business ethics*, 85(2), 285-301.
- [8] Moharana, S. (2013). Corporate social responsibility: A study of selected public sector banks in India. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 15(4), 1-9.
- [9] Márquez, A., & Fombrun, C. J. (2005). Measuring corporate social responsibility. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 7(4), 304-308.
- [10] Burianová, L., & Paulík, J. (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility in commercial banking-a case study from the Czech Republic. *Journal of competitiveness*.6(1), 50-70.
- [11] Dogra, A., & Dogra, M. (2019). Sustainability and Ethical Banking: A Case Study of Punjab National Bank. *Amity Journal of Corporate Governance*, 4(1), 15-27.
- [12] Márquez, A., & Fombrun, C. J. (2005). Measuring corporate social responsibility. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 7(4), 304-308. Tai, F. M., & Chuang, S. H. (2014). Corporate social responsibility. *Ibusiness*, 6(03), 117.
- [13] Tai, F. M., & Chuang, S. H. (2014). Corporate social responsibility. *Ibusiness*, 6(03), 117. Method
- [14] Mita, A. F., Ray, S., Haque, M., & Saikat, M. H. (2023). Prediction and optimization of properties of concrete containing crushed stone dust and nylon fiber using response surface ology. *Heliyon*, 9(3), 1-18.

- [15] Smith, N. C. (2003). Corporate social responsibility: whether or how?. *California management review*, 45(4), 52-76.
- [16] Bordolo, N., & Mukherje, D. K. (2017). A Comparative Study On The Csr Activities Of Public And Private Sector Commercial Banks. *International Journal Of Interdisciplinary Research In Science Society And Culture*, 3(1), 22-28.
- [17] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Study on ABCD analysis technique for business models, business strategies, operating concepts & business systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 95-115.
- [18] Shenoy, V., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). ABCD Analysis of On-line Campus Placement Model. *IRA International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 5(2), 227-244.
- [19] Varambally, K. V. M., & Aithal, P. S. (2009). Mobile Business Technology and Business Proliferation of Banks—A futuristic Approach. *Amity Business Review—an Indian Journal*, 10(1), 9-25.
- [20] Aithal, P. S., & Varambally, K. V. M. (2015). Customer perspective on online mobile banking in india-an empirical study. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(7), 77-97.
- [21] Nath, V., Nayak, N., & Goel, A. (2014). Green banking practices—A review. *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Business Management (IMPACT: IJRBM)*, 2(1), 45-62.
- [22] Yadav, R., & Pathak, G. (2013). Environmental sustainability through green banking: A study on International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE), 5(2), 37-48.
- [23] Moon, J. (2007). The contribution of corporate social responsibility to sustainable development. *Sustainable development*, 15(5), 296-306.
- [24] Barnett, M. L. (2007). Stakeholder influence capacity and the variability of financial returns to corporate social responsibility. *Academy of management review*, 32(3), 794-816.
- [25] Hebbar, C. K., & Mahale, P. (2019). Impact of Demonetization on Green Banking. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 19(4), 40-45.
- [26] Soni, D., & Mehta, P. (2020). Manifestation of Internal CSR on Employee Engagement: Mediating Role of Organizational Trust. *Indian Journal Industrial Relations*, 55(3), 441-45.
- [27] Pomeroy, A., & Dolnicar, S. (2009). Assessing the prerequisite of successful CSR implementation: are consumers aware of CSR initiatives? *Journal of business ethics*, 85(2), 285-301.
- [28] Adeyanju, O. D. (2012). An assessment of the impact of corporate social responsibility on Nigerian society: The examples of banking and communication industries. *Universal Journal of Marketing and Business Research*, 1(1), 17-43.
- [29] Budhwar, P. S., & Boyne, G. (2004). Human resource management in the Indian public and private sectors: an empirical comparison. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(2), 346-370.
- [30] Keffas, G., & Olulu-Briggs, O. V. (2011). Corporate social responsibility: How does it affect the financial performance of banks? Empirical evidence from US, UK and Japan. *Journal of management and corporate governance*, 3(1), 8-26.
- [31] Alafi, K., & Hasoneh, A. B. (2012). Corporate social responsibility associated with customer satisfaction and financial performance a case study with Housing Banks in Jordan. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(15), 102-115.
- [32] Patjoshi, P. K., & Nayak, U. (2020). Impact of CSR on Financial Performance: A Study on Banking Companies in India. *International Journal of Modern Agriculture*, 9(3), 953-962.
- [33] Hu, V. I., & Scholtens, B. (2014) Corporate social responsibility policies of commercial banks in developing countries. *Sustainable Development*, 22(4), 276-288.
- [34] Aithal, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). ABCD analysis of Dye-doped Polymers for Photonic Applications. *IRA-International Journal of Applied Sciences*, 4(3), 358-378.
- [35] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Application of ABCD Analysis Model for Black Ocean Strategy. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(10), 331-337.
- [36] Malaysia, P. (2019). Internal corporate social responsibility practices and employees' job satisfaction in a Malaysian Banking company. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, 55(1), 97-109.
- [37] Jie, C. T., & Hasan, N. A. M. (2018). Predictors of employees' job satisfaction through corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices in Malaysian banking company. *Advanced Science Letters*, 24(5), 3072-3078.
- [38] Rosati, F., Costa, R., Calabrese, A., & Pedersen, E. R. G. (2018). Employee attitudes towards corporate social responsibility: a study on gender, age and educational level differences. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 25(6), 1306-1319.

-
- [39] Belás, J. (2012). Social responsibility and ethics in the banking business: Myth or reality? A case study from the Slovak Republic. *Economic annals*, 57(195), 115-137.
- [40] Bolanle, A. B., Adebisi, S. O., & Muyideen, A. A. (2012). Corporate social responsibility and profitability of Nigeria banks- a causal relationship. *Research Journal of finance and accounting*, 3(1), 6-17.
- [41] Belas, J., Čera, G., Dvorský, J., & Čepel, M. (2021). Corporate social responsibility and sustainability issues of small-and medium-sized enterprises. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(2), 721-730.
- [42] Adeyanju, O. D. (2012). An assessment of the impact of corporate social responsibility on Nigerian society: The examples of banking and communication industries. *Universal Journal of Marketing and Business Research*, 1(1), 17-43.
- [43] Budhwar, P. S., & Boyne, G. (2004). Human resource management in the Indian public and private sectors: an empirical comparison. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(2), 346-370.
- [44] Smith, N. C. (2003). Corporate social responsibility: whether or how?. *California management review*, 45(4), 52-76.
- [45] Bhaskar A. & Hebbar, C. K. (2020). E-Banking: Technology for Cashless Society- A Study on Indian Banking Industry. *Studies in Indian Place Names*, 40(70), 579 –586.